

Disease Control of Apricot Trees

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ABSTRACT: The article provides information about apricot diseases and their types. *Wilsonomyces carpophilus* is the fungus that causes apricot shot holes. It spends the winter on diseased buds as well as twigs. During winter and spring showers, as well as when water splashes up from the ground, the spores on these sections of the tree might be transported. Because those spores require 24 hours of moisture to develop in and induce infection, damp and humid circumstances are conducive to disease propagation. Apricot tree illnesses may wreck years of labor in a matter of days, yet the majority of apricot tree diseases are easily identified, treated, and sometimes prevented. Here's all you need to know about apricot tree diseases.

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INTRODUCTION

An apricot tree may encounter problems as it matures, such as pests or illnesses. Location, weather, and upkeep all have a role in determining which problems your apricot tree faces and how well it handles them. Disease-resistant apricot trees provide low-spray or no-spray options for producers who desire a low-spray or no-spray orchard, and consistent maintenance can help keep most issues at bay for all apricot trees.

Apricots demand some attention from the gardener in order to produce great yields and good-quality fruits. You can rapidly act and solve the problem if you discover an illness or the advent of a bug in time. When producing apricots, it's important to know what pests might attack them, how to prevent them, and how to combat them. At first appearance, the apricot appears to be a thermophilic and difficult-to-care-for plant. Frequently exposed to a variety of fungal and viral diseases that can harm the entire plant, including the bark, leaves, flowers, and fruits. To properly deal with the enemy, you must first get to know him in person, and even better, do not let him near the apricot trees. It is possible (and required) to avoid the appearance of illnesses and not to bring them to treatment by taking early and competent preventive measures.

Wilsonomyces carpophilus is the fungus that causes apricot shot holes. It spends the winter on diseased buds as well as twigs. During winter and spring showers, as well as when water splashes up from the ground, the spores on these sections of the tree might be transported. Because those spores require 24 hours of moisture to develop in and induce infection, damp and humid circumstances are conducive to disease propagation. Shot hole disease affects apricots in a number of ways, but the term originates from the spots that appear on the leaves and subsequently fall off, leaving small holes. Purple patches on new shoots, buds, and leaves are the earliest indicators of apricot shot hole fungal disease on trees in the spring. In the spring, purple spots on young shoots, buds, and leaves are the first signs of apricot shot hole fungal disease on trees. The spots on leaves that develop into holes start off small and often have a yellow or light green border. Even in the spring, severe diseases can cause the leaves to fall off prematurely. As the fruit ripens, it develops a widespread infection that causes scabby, rough spots on the top of the fruit that may flake off, leaving rough patches behind.

1. *Picture (Wilsonomyces carpophilus, Colorado State University)*

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Apricot trees might go through a general decline one year and then just disappear the next spring. Armillaria root rot, commonly known as oak root fungus, is a common cause of this type of apricot decline.

A year or two before the entire tree collapses, apricot trees infected with this disease display a general reduction in vigor. As the fungus spreads, it usually creates a circular region in an orchard where every tree is infected. The fungus spreads from diseased trees to healthy trees via their roots. In late spring, a tree may leaf out and die, but more often than not, the tree does not. Armillaria root rot may also affect peaches.

Bacterial canker appears in the spring as well. Sometimes limbs die back, but most commonly, amber-colored oozing on the trunk is the first symptom. Spots on the leaves and strange patterns on immature shoots are possible. These structures, known as blasts, wrap the shoot in a transparent ooze before it dies.

2. **Picture** (*Armillaria Root Rot*)

3. **Picture** (*Bacterial Canker*)

Outside of the canker-killed sections, there may be orange and red specks on the tree. The tree may try to live by producing multiple suckers around the ground level or from limbs before the diseased areas of the tree. *Pseudomonas syringae*, the bacterium that causes bacterial canker, resides on the tree's surface and is transmitted by splashing rain. When the weather is warm and moist in the spring, it multiplies. When the illness sprays on healthy plants, it will not spread, but stressed trees will.

Whether that is cloudy or wet is ideal for the development of fungal diseases. However, if you follow the advice of skilled gardeners, the chances of an apricot contracting a fungus are almost none. The absence of illness and the negative impacts of hazardous insects will aid in the production of a plentiful crop and healthy plant growth.

In the spring, the plant needs the most attention. The tree needs to be fed and safeguarded from hazardous insects and illnesses at this time. Whitewashing the trunks with lime diluted in water is recommended. Spray the foliage with fungicidal solutions such as "Skor," "Horus," or "Switch" after a few days.

Use insecticidal chemicals such as Actelika and Karbofosa to keep pests at bay. Remember that each chemical agent has the potential to be addictive. Insects, for example, may acquire resistance to certain medications. As a result, it's a good idea to switch up your methods on a regular basis.

The leaf crown must be pruned on a regular basis. This will not only make the tree look more well-kept and tidy, but it will also allow you to prune out old branches. The plant is given urea treatment before the first leaves develop. 7 g of powder per 10 liters of water is the ratio that must be followed. This treatment not only saturates the apricot tree with all of the essential elements and vitamins it requires for healthy growth, but it also eliminates the majority of the pests that have settled on it. This medication should be used with great caution and according to the manufacturer's instructions on the label.

CONCLUSIONS

To begin, use a garden var. to treat any mechanical damage to the bark. Whitewash the trunk with lime on a regular basis, but this time combine the agent with copper sulfate. When yellow clay is added to the mix, the protection becomes more moisture-resistant, allowing it to last considerably longer.

A 3% Bordeaux composition is especially helpful in the fall for suppressing foci of a spreading fungus. It's highly efficient against gray rot and stone fruit scab in the early stages. It will be most practical to use a spray gun with a big nozzle, which will allow you to treat not only the apricot tree's bark but also the lower portion of the crown, which is particularly vulnerable to the impacts of dangerous insects.

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Remove and burn all afflicted sections of the plant without fail, then process the slices. It's also a good idea to get rid of fallen leaves since hazardous insects might hide in them and then migrate to a tree's bark.

You may not only keep an apricot tree healthy but also acquire a nice crop by following easy suggestions for caring for it. The early phases of the battle against numerous diseases and pests are critical, as they reduce the possibility of unfavorable effects on the culture.

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